

Hot Water Degradation of Natural Fiber Reinforced SMC

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SUMMARY

In this study, the hot water degradation of the SMC in which reinforcement was jute cloth was evaluated. As a result, it was found that the fracture mechanism changed from the combination of crack propagation in matrix area and delamination in the interface around the fiber bundle to only crack propagation in matrix area by the water immersion.

Keywords: SMC, Jute, Sheet Molding Compound, natural fiber, water immersion

INTRODUCTION

Sheet Molding Compound (SMC) is most common thermoset-based molding compound that the reinforcement is impregnated by resin with filler, thickener and other additives. FRP products can be manufactured easily by using this SMC sheet. Mass production can be adopted because SMC process has high volume and high speed molding cycle. That is to say, SMC technique requires lower cost than hand-lay-up and resin injection (RI) techniques. And SMC has high strength, resistance of corrosion and water proof. Therefore, SMC products are used in various fields such as automotive, marine and industrial applications today^[1-12].

Recent earth environmental concern requires easy recycle material system, and the use of biodegradable polymer and natural fiber is noticed in composite materials. To apply the natural fiber for the structural parts, the use as reinforcement of SMC is desirable because it is expected that SMC can be used in various fields in terms of high productivity and dimensional stability. Considering that fiber reinforced composite is used for structural part, the use of long-span must be possible. Therefore, the evaluation of the durability such as degradation is very important subject.

In this study, SMC that reinforcement was jute cloth was prepared. The jute cloth reinforced SMC was immersed in hot water to promote the degradation. And after immersion, an increase ratio of water and bending properties were compared with that of jute cloth reinforced SMC without immersion.

SPECIMENS AND EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Jute cloths and unsaturated polyester resin were used as reinforcement and as matrix respectively in composite materials. A photograph of used jute cloth is shown in Figure 1. The jute cloth was prepared with dry processing in 80 degrees for 6 hour.

At first, the cloth prepreg sheet was made by using sheeting equipment as shown in Figure 2. And 2 cloth prepreg sheets were laminated and SMC panels were manufactured by 100ton compression machine. Molding temperature and pressure were 175 degrees for upper die and 160 degrees for lower die, and 10MPa. The weight fraction of the reinforcement was 20%. The dimension and the thickness of the panels were 300mm x 300mm and around 3.6mm respectively. Afterward, the panel was cut into the specimen with the width of 10mm and the length of 80mm.

In the immersion test, the weight of specimens was measured before immersion at first. Secondary, specimens were exposed to water at the temperature of 80 degrees for 0h, 3h, 10h, 30h, 50h, 98h, 193h, 288h, 384h and 504h. After immersion, the weight of specimens was measured immediately. Finally, specimens were dried at 80 degrees for 6 hours.

Three point bending tests were performed on condition of testing speed 2mm/min by using INSTRON universal testing machine (type 4206) to investigate the durability of specimen with hot water immersion. The span length was 60mm. Cross-sectional observation of fracture area was performed to investigate the degradation behaviour in each immersed specimen.

Figure 1 Jute cloth

Figure 2 Sheeting equipment

RESULTS

Evaluation of Weight Changes^[13]

The following three formulas were used to evaluate the change of weight in the case of long term exposure.

$$Ma = \frac{W_w - W_i}{W_i} \quad (1)$$

$$Mg = \frac{W_w - W_d}{W_i} \quad (2)$$

$$Ml = \frac{W_i - W_d}{W_i} = Mg - Ma \quad (3)$$

where “ Ma ” is the apparent ratio of absorbed water, “ Mg ” is the net weight gain due to water absorption and “ MI ” is the weight loss. “ W_i ” is the weight before immersion, “ W_w ” is the weight after immersion and “ W_d ” is the weight after dry process in 80 degrees for 6 hours.

Relationship between Ma and square root of immersion time is shown in Figure 3. It was found that the content of water in the specimen was saturated from around 50h. The value of Ma in the saturated state was about 7%. Next, relationship between Mg and square root of immersion time is shown in Figure 4. As this result, the content of water until around 50h was same as Ma . However, the content of water started to increase after immersion time 50h. Then, weight loss, MI was calculated. Figure 5 shows relationship between MI and square root of immersion time. MI was almost constant zero. value until the immersion time 50h. However, MI started to increase after 50h as same Mg . Therefore, it was considered that when the immersion time exceeded 50h, the resin or the jute fiber was lost by long immersion.

Figure 3 Ma and immersion time

Figure 4 Mg and immersion time

Figure 5 MI and immersion time

Bending Properties

To evaluate the durability of the SMC, effects of water immersion on the mechanical properties of jute cloth reinforced SMC were investigated by way of three point bending test. Relationship between bending modulus and square root of immersion time are shown in Figure 6. Bending modulus decreased in immersion time from 0h to 50h. However, when the immersion time exceeded 50h, the bending modulus became constant value. Relationship between bending strength and square root of immersion time is shown in Figure 7. Strength also decreased in immersion time from 0h to 50h. And the bending strength became constant value after 50h.

Figure 6 Modulus and immersion time

Figure 7 Strength and immersion time

Cross-sectional Observation

Cross-sectional observations of fracture area in final fracture were performed. Photographs and schematic illustrations of cross-section at immersion time 0h, 50h, 98h and 504h are shown in Figure 8-11 (a) and (b).

In the immersion time “0h”, a delamination around weft fiber bundle and a large crack in a horizontal direction could be seen. In immersion time “50h”, a delamination around weft fiber bundle and the crack in a horizontal direction in a central matrix area could be seen. In the immersion time “98h”, a delamination in the interface around weft fiber bundle could be seen and the crack propagated with breaking of warp fiber bundle. In the immersion time “504h”, one large crack and two small cracks in a vertical direction could be seen in the matrix area.

(a) Photograph

(a) Photograph

(b) Schematic illustration

Figure 8 Immersion time “0h”

(b) Schematic illustration

Figure 9 Immersion time “50h”

(c) Photograph

(b) Schematic illustration

Figure 10 Immersion time “98h”

(a) Photograph

(b) Schematic illustration

Figure 11 Immersion time “504h”

Therefore, it was thought that the fracture mechanism changed by the immersion in hot water and the change point was between 50h and 98h. In early stage such as immersion time “0h” and “50h”, the main fracture was the interfacial delamination around fiber bundle and crack propagation from the interface of weft fiber bundle because the interfacial bonding strength tended to decrease owing to the degradation by water immersion. However, in the immersion time “98h” and “504h”, cracks in the matrix area were dominant on the fracture. Especially, in immersion time “504h”, no delamination could be seen. That is to say, the main fracture was crack propagation in the matrix area.

CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the degradation of jute cloth reinforced SMC was evaluated by promotional testing of hot water immersion. As a result, bending properties decreased as the immersion time increased. And the bending properties were constant after immersion time 50h.

From the cross sectional observation, it was found that the fracture mechanism changed from the combination of crack propagation and delamination in the interface around the weft fiber bundle to only crack propagation in matrix area by water immersion. Especially the change point was between 50h and 98h. The improvement of both the durability of the matrix resin and the interfacial bending strength around the weft fiber bundle is important for the durability of jute cloth reinforced SMC.

References

1. E.V. Morozov, K. E. Morozov, V. Selvarajalu. *Composite Structure*, 62, 361-366 (2003).

2. Hamada, H, Hidekuma, Y, Asami, N, De Coninck, M, Sarata, M, Technical Papers, Regional Technical Conference - Society of Plastics Engineers, Volume 4, pp.2019-2022 (2008)
3. Liu, W., Thayer, K., Misra, M., Drzal, L. T., Mohanty, A. K., Polymer Engineering and Science 47 (7), pp.969-976 (2007)
4. Hapuarachchi, T. D., Ren, G., Fan, M., Hogg, P. J., Pejis, T., Applied Composite Materials 14 (4), pp.251-264 (2007)
5. Flanigan, C., Williams, K., Lee, E., Houston, D., Mielewski, D., Global Plastics Environmental Conference 2005: GPEC2005 – Creating Sustainability for the Environment, pp.27-40 (2005)
6. Mehta, G., Mohanty, A. K., Thayer, K., Misra, M., Drzal, L. T., Journal of Polymers and the Environment 13 (2), pp.169-175 (2005)
7. Mehta, G., Mohanty, A. K., Tahyer, K., Drzal, L. T., Misra, M., Global Plastics Environmental Conference 2004 – Plastics: Helping Grow a Greener Environment, GPEC2004, pp.317-326 (2004)
8. Goswami, D. N., Jha, P. C., Mahato, K., Indian Journal of Chemical Technology 11 (1), pp.67-73 (2004)
9. Van Voorn, B., Smit, H. H. G., Sinke, R. J., De Klerk, B., Composites – PartA: Applied Science and Manufacturing 32 (9), pp.1271-1279 (2001)
10. Bledzki, A. K., Gassan, J., Progress in Polymer Science (Oxford) 24 (2), pp.221-274 (1999)
11. Williams, K. A., Flanigan, C. M., Lee, E. C., Mielewski, D. F., Houston, D. Q., AIChE Annual Meeting, Conference Proceeding, pp.9359-9372 (2007)
12. Knouff, B., Atchinson, R., International SAMPE Technical Conference 33, pp.1428-1437 (2001)
13. Tohru Morii, *Doctor thesis*, 14-34 (1994)